

A suite of geospatial online services for education and research

Over the last decade, JISC has contributed to the development of geospatial services through the funding of research and development at the JISC National Datacentres and by central negotiation and licensing of datasets. The development of services to deliver these datasets has widened access to essential material that many institutions would not otherwise have been able to afford.

This means that the UK education and research community has much greater resources at its disposal – contemporary and historical Ordnance Survey map data, geological map data, marine and coastal zone map data from **Digimap**, the **Go-Geo!** online resource discovery tool and satellite imagery from the **Landmap Service**.

For modest fees, institutions can access the **Digimap** suite of services, which vary according to an institution's JISC Band. The negotiations managed by JISC Collections deliver substantial cost savings and efficiency gains. These benefits, combined with favourable licensing terms and conditions, ensure that institutions get value for money when subscribing to resources. Funding from JISC has made the **Landmap Service** and **Go-Geo!** free of charge to universities, colleges and research councils in the UK.

As **Digimap - Ordnance Survey Collection**, **Geology Digimap**, **Historic Digimap** and **Marine Digimap** are based on the same platform, users can seamlessly use all four services, to create a continuous layer of geographical information that encompasses both land and sea, thus enabling research projects which would otherwise be arduous, time consuming or even impossible.

This brochure provides a catalogue of the JISC funded geospatial services. These services provide online access to datasets that are being used across a multitude of subject areas, often in innovative ways, to enrich teaching, learning and research.

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Digimap - Ordnance Survey Collection

This service, which is hosted at EDINA, the JISC national datacentre, delivers Ordnance Survey maps and map data, available either via download facilities for use with appropriate application software such as GIS or CAD, or as maps generated by Digimap online. A simple mapping tool allows users to view and print maps of any location in Great Britain at a series of predefined scales; a more advanced mapping tool enables the user to specify map scale, area and content, as well as print maps at up to A0 in size. Below is a list of examples showing how Ordnance Survey maps and map data from Digimap can be used:

- computer science - by using maps in a CAD program as an example of computer graphics applications
- earth sciences - to identify sources of pollutants in a particular area
- engineering - to investigate environmental features for a particular site or area as part of an environmental impact assessment
- geography - to develop cartographic skills and using the map data in GIS to develop students' Information Technology (IT) skills using the map data in GIS
- history - to investigate the historical development of a particular area or to identify sites of historic interest
- skills for life - by using maps as common 2-D representations of 3-D objects for the Adult Numeracy level 2 unit
- social care and policy - by combining map data with census and local population data to analyse inequalities of social care provision in a particular region
- surveying - to support modules on IT and GIS
- town & country planning - to investigate land use or as a starting point for research into developing sustainable communities and transport

www.jisc-collections.ac.uk/digimapos

- agricultural and countryside management - by using local maps for landscape assessment and planning modules, in particular for identifying different types of landscapes, land use, combining the map data with survey data, photographs and site surveys to assist in uncovering relevant planning issues to be resolved and apply appropriate planning policies and recommendations
- archaeology - to support modules on computer applications in archaeology and landscape surveying

Geology Digimap

This online service provides geological map data from the British Geological Survey. Geology Digimap offers a fascinating insight into the earth's physical structure and substance, its history, and the processes that act on it by delivering digital geological map data of Great Britain. Made available by JISC Collections, through EDINA's Digimap platform, this resource includes onshore geological data covering bedrock geology, superficial deposits, mass movement and artificial ground, as well as a whole range of linear features such as faults and fossil beds. The resource also contains the BGS Lexicon of Named Rock Units, to provide a wealth of detailed material.

Many disciplines require information about the rocks that lie beneath our cities, towns and countryside. Below is a list of examples showing how this service can be used:

- agricultural studies - to help identify soil type to determine what type of vegetation can be grown in certain locations
- archaeology - to relate finds of building materials and stone artefacts to their likely sources
- architecture and civil engineering - to survey sites and for geotechnical modelling whereby the suitability of the land on a proposed site is assessed on factors such as its structure, stability and drainage, as this will determine how buildings should be designed and built

- coastal management and sciences, earth sciences, environmental management and sciences - to identify land-fill sites and contaminated land in order to develop waste management strategies
- geography - to support geology modules

www.jisc-collections.ac.uk/geologydigimap

Historic Digimap

Historic Digimap, which is hosted at EDINA, the JISC national datacentre, delivers historical Ordnance Survey maps as georeferenced images, available either to view on screen or to download for use with appropriate application software such as GIS or CAD. The service allows users to view and print historic maps of any location in Great Britain

from 1843–1995 at a range of scales, making it an ideal service for a number of subject areas including:

- agriculture - to identify various forms of land use over time on an environmental management and planning module
- civil engineering - to identify brownfield sites, investigating environmental features and site surveying
- earth sciences - to investigate environmental changes in a chosen area over time
- environmental studies - to identify landfill sites and other forms of land use over time
- geography - to research the history of landscapes in the UK and changes in human geography

- history - to undertake interdisciplinary research in tracing the development of the local area
- planning - to evaluate past planning decisions or for site development appraisals
- social sciences - to investigate the development of communities in a particular geographic area over time

The Historical Town Plans, GOAD Fire Insurance Plans and Green Belt Data datasets from Landmark Information Group will be added to Historic Digimap at no extra charge to existing subscribing institutions.

www.jisc-collections.ac.uk/historicdigimap

Marine Digimap

This new service, which is hosted at EDINA, the JISC national datacentre, delivers marine and coastal zone mapping from SeaZone Solutions Ltd. It includes raster marine maps of various scales and detail (derived from Admiralty Charts), which are ideal for backdrop mapping in the UK coastal zone, and Hydrospatial, a vector thematic marine data product suitable for advanced spatial analysis and customised mapping. Users can view maps through their web browser, save maps for printing and download the map data for use in geographical information systems.

The Hydrospatial product includes key geographical information on the UK marine and coastal zone environment provided as six

logically structured Topic Layers. This includes data on: the nature and shape of the earth's surface on land and under the sea; marine biological, physical and chemical features; man-made physical structures and obstructions; socio-economic information (like aquaculture, fisheries, and transportation routes); conservation areas and data on tides and currents.

Marine Digimap can be used across a broad range of subject areas, for example in:

- archaeology - to support modules focusing on environmental archaeology and the use of digital data for archaeology & anthropology
- biology - to support modules focusing on ecology
- engineering - to investigate environmental features and site surveying to develop engineering solutions for

construction projects such as oilrig construction and marine-based wind turbines

- environmental science and management - to support studies to protect the marine environment and to assist in developing coastal protection strategies
- maritime studies - to monitor and protect natural heritage such as fish stocks and other marine wildlife
- ocean & earth sciences - to investigate the marine geological environment within a particular area

www.jisc-collections.ac.uk/marinedigimap

Go-Geo!

Go-Geo! is a free online resource discovery tool, operated and maintained at EDINA, the JISC national datacentre. It allows for the identification and retrieval of records describing the content, quality, condition and other characteristics of geospatial data that exist within UK tertiary education and beyond.

Go-Geo! enables users to:

- Find data: using Go-Geo! to search and discover geospatial data via a simple or an advanced search engine
- Find geographic information: with the ability to search for other related resources, such as books, photographs, projects and maps, for specific geographic areas of interest
- Discover ideas and resources: a variety of geographic information resource channels provide comprehensive up-to-date information on news, major data providers, online resources, software, standards, geotermiology, GI organisations, learning and research, training courses, conferences, events and books
- Learn about geospatial metadata: a section dedicated to supporting the creation of metadata for geospatial data

www.gogeo.ac.uk

Landmap Service

This service, which is hosted at Mimas, the JISC national datacentre, provides access to and support for a range of satellite imagery for the British Isles for research and teaching purposes. Funding from JISC has made this service free of charge to UK universities, colleges and research councils. It provides UK coverage of both Optical and Radar satellite imagery from spacecraft such as Landsat, SPOT, ERS and ENVISAT.

The Landmap Service also provides elevation data including a Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of the whole of the British Isles at 25 metre resolution. Landmap Service datasets can be used with image or graphics software,

or with other mapping data, e.g. Ordnance Survey, as they are orthorectified in geotiff format and projected to British National Grid.

New datasets, which cover the main conurbations of the UK are now included in the service: Modern Aerial Photography orthorectified (2003 - 2007); Historical Aerial Photography orthorectified (1940 - 1950); LiDAR DSM and DTM (1 - 2m resolution) for 75 cities and towns including London (2007); Land use, Building class and Building Heights (2001 - 2007) and Near Infra-Red (NIR) imagery.

Landmap learning materials include a series of image processing courses for remote sensing available free of charge to registered institutions. These courses currently comprises ten modules covering: information

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extraction; spectral mapping; georeferencing images; structural mapping; vegetation mapping; land cover classification; meteorology and sea-surface temperature mapping; coastal mapping; integration with GIS; and mineral exploitation. The course content is due to expand in the future with additions including the use of radar, hyperspectral data and atmospheric correction.

This resource can be used across a range of subject areas including:

- archaeology - to assist in the assessment of archaeological sites and complement excavation techniques
- biological sciences - to analyse marine, coastal and mountainous environments to assist in developing strategies

to protect the environment or for studying the effects of climate change

- countryside management - to identify different types of landscapes, land use and site surveying
- engineering - using satellite imagery for surveying and terrain modelling
- environmental science - to analyse land cover change, biophysical properties of vegetation and for ecosystem modelling
- retail management - to identify prime retail locations

www.jisc-collections.ac.uk/landmap

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